

Thermodynamics of Hydrophobic Hydration*

J. C. AHLUWALIA

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, New Delhi-110 029

THE topic of my lecture is "Thermodynamics of Hydrophobic Hydration"; a subject in which I have been carrying out research for the last several years. Since the realization of the importance of hydrophobic hydration and hydrophobic interaction in a variety of biochemical and biological processes, some twenty years ago¹⁻⁴ the studies of this phenomenon have been attracting increasing attention. It is a well known fact that hydrocarbons do not dissolve in water. The unfavourable process of dissolution of hydrocarbons ($\Delta G > 0$) is a consequence of negative hydration entropy ($\Delta S < 0$) the enthalpy effects being small. The negative entropy of hydration is interpreted as resulting from enhancement of structure of neighbouring water molecules surrounding the hydrocarbon as shown in Fig. 1 (a).

Fig. 1. Diagrammatic representation of (a) Hydrophobic Hydration and (b) Hydrophobic Interaction.
From : Ref. 7.

This special type of interaction of non-polar groups with water is known as hydrophobic hydration⁵. The association or aggregation of apolar groups which is known as hydrophobic interaction should then be regarded as partial reversal of the thermodynamically unfavourable process of solution and is shown in Fig. 1 (b). The reversible aggregation of molecules with large apolar groups in the case of surfactants, phospholipids glycerides, and dyestuffs and the folding of globular proteins is believed to depend on the phenomenon of hydrophobic association^{6,7}.

The peculiar features exhibited by aqueous solutions of hydrocarbons or solutes having apolar groups with one or two functional groups have been attributed to the peculiarity of water as solvent. In order to understand the phenomenon of hydrophobic hydration it is therefore essential to understand the structure of liquid water.

The structures of water in the gaseous and solid states are well established and are illustrated in Figs. 2 and 3 respectively. Water in the gaseous state exists as monomer molecules with sp^3 hybridised bonding having tetrahedral geometry (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Approximate geometric relation of nuclei and electron charge distribution in a water molecule.
From : Ref. 16.

Water in the solid states, as established at atmospheric pressure by neutron scattering studies, exists in ice I form (Fig. 3) with each water molecule having two covalent bonds and two hydrogen bonds such that each oxygen is tetrahedrally oriented to other oxygen atoms, resulting in an open structure.

Fig. 3. Schematic representation of the crystal structure of ice at low pressure. From : Ref. 27.

* LOURDU M. YEDDANAPALLI MEMORIAL LECTURE (1975) delivered on April 3, 1977 at Loyala Collage, Madras.

However, it is the structure of liquid water which is still not understood in an unambiguous way in spite of extensive studies made during the last decade. There are many review articles and books which deal extensively with the subject of liquid water¹⁸⁻²⁰. Theoretical models proposed to depict the bulk structure can be broadly classified into continuum²¹⁻²³ and mixture¹⁵⁻²⁴ models.

According to continuum models liquid water is treated as a uniform dielectric medium and the environment about a particular molecule is considered to be the same as about any other molecule so that the behaviour of all molecules is equivalent. According to the mixture models, liquid water is visualised to comprise of two or more distinguishable species. Even according to the supporters of the mixtures approach toward defining the intermolecular structure of water there are differences of opinion about the particular form of the species present in liquid water. As a result, many models have been proposed which can be categorised under the mixture concept. Among the notable mixtures models are the following :

- (i) Self Clathrate model of Pauling²² (Fig. 4).
- (ii) Interstitial model of Samoilov¹⁵.

Fig. 4. Diagrammatic representation of self-clathrate model of liquid water of Pauling. From : Ref. 32.

- (iii) Flickering cluster model of Frank and Wen²⁵ (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Frank and Wen Flickering Cluster model of liquid water. From : Ref. 27.

The most popular of these mixture models is that of Frank and Wen²⁵ which visualizes the existence of short lived (half life time $\sim 10^{-11}$ sec) clusters of highly hydrogen bonded bulkier water molecules mixed with denser nonbonded monomers.

Any acceptable model must account for all the properties of water such as maximum in the density (or minimum in the molar volume) around 4°, anomalous PVT, heat capacity, viscosity and acoustic absorption of water, in addition to results of X-ray scattering and spectroscopic studies. The properties like maximum of density (Fig. 6) can best

Fig. 6. The phenomenon of maximum density of water. Effect of changing temperature upon the molar volume of water. From : Ref. 9.

be accounted in terms of balance between the increase in vibration amplitude with increase in temperature (first neighbour distance increasing with temperature causing increase in volume with temperature) and the collapse of open ice-like bulky structure with increase in temperature (angular deformation increasing with temperature causing decrease in volume with temperature).

The results derived from X-ray studies indicate that the positional correlation between molecules, that is structure in liquid water, extends only over relatively short distances. Near the melting point the average separation between oxygen atoms from neighbouring water molecules is only slightly larger than that found in ordinary ice (2.77Å). The near neighbour distance increases from 2.84Å at 4° to 2.94Å at 200° and the corresponding maximum in the correlation function $g(r)$ broadens progressively with increasing temperature. The change in position and shape of the O---O peak reflect the weakening of the O---H---O hydrogen bond at high temperature. The average coordination number in liquid water is independent of temperature from 4. to 200° and is slightly larger than four, indicating predominantly tetrahedral coordination. The peak corresponding to near neighbour O.....O interactions cannot be described as a single Gaussian distance distribution and this complexity of the first coordination shell of a given water molecule must be due to the presence in the liquid of molecules with at best two types of near-neighbour configurations. However, the small angle X-ray scattering results indicate that liquid water is single phase,

homogeneous and isotropic. Of the structures which have a sufficiently detailed basis to permit calculation of radial distribution functions, only the Ice I model has been shown to give agreement with the data from both large and small angle X-ray scattering⁸.

Even though the mixture model seems to have an edge over continuum model in accounting for many of the bulk properties mentioned above none of the models can be thought of as unique in representing the structure of liquid water. The study and analysis of macroscopic properties of water have not led to an unambiguous description of liquid water in terms of whether it consists of one kind of molecules or more than one kind of molecules. It is but natural that one would look into the properties of water which describe the behaviour at micro level. In this regard a number of workers have studied the uncoupled O-H and O-D stretching frequency of the HOD molecules in the Infrared and Raman spectrum.

I will mention briefly only the more recent and significant studies made by G. Walrafen²⁹ using laser Raman spectroscopy. Walrafen was able to analyse the broad O-D stretching band of D₂O in H₂O into component bands centered near 2620 and 2520 cm⁻¹ which could be assigned to OD stretching frequencies of non hydrogen bonded and hydrogen bonded species. This assignment was further supported by the finding (Fig 7) that with the

Fig. 7. Argon-ion-laser Raman spectra from a 6.2M solution of D₂O in H₂O at 25° and 62°. From : Ref. 29.

increase in temperature the relative intensity of the 2620 cm⁻¹ band increased and that of 2520 cm⁻¹ decreased as expected from the decrease in H-bonding on heating. This could be called first ever experimental evidence in support of mixture model concept of water. The proponents of the continuum model are still not convinced about this and they believe that there must be broadness of local geometries to produce broadness of the spectroscopic bands.

On the theoretical side recently there has been some significant progress as a result of molecular

dynamical calculations by Rahman and Stillinger²⁵⁻²⁹. The results of these calculations is that liquid water is seen to be very complicated. There is a great distribution of geometries and bond strengths ranging from very strong to hydrogen bonds that are not bonded at all, a type of situation which makes proponents of both continuum and mixture models happy.

For workers who are interested in the structure of solution or the effect of solutes on the structure of water, the situation is still a confusing one for lack of well defined structure of water. However, they tend to favour the mixture concept without which it becomes difficult to rationalise the effect of solutes on water. Further more, it is the Frank and Wen²⁵ flickering cluster model developed by Némethy and Scheraga²⁷ which the solution workers find as the most useful one. Even though this model is not entirely adequate, it has been able to account for the properties of aqueous solutes more satisfactorily than any other model. I will, therefore, use this model for describing the behaviour of aqueous solutes notwithstanding the present status of structure of liquid water.

Thermodynamics of Hydrophobic Hydration :

According to the mixture model of Frank & Wen²⁵, the water molecules can be considered to be in dynamic equilibrium between the bulky tetrahedrally hydrogen bonded clusters and the denser monomer molecules as represented by $(H_2O)_n \rightleftharpoons H_2O(d)$. When a solute is dissolved in water it is assumed that the former may shift the equilibrium in either direction. A solute which causes the shift so as to increase the number and the average half-life of the cluster is termed a structure maker and a solute which has an effect in the opposite direction is called a structure-breaker. Although the concept of structure-making and breaking of solutes is not entirely satisfactory, it has proved useful in the study of effects of solutes on water structure. These effects can be detected experimentally by observing the changes brought about by the solutes in the properties of water such as fluidity (reorientation time and increase in viscosity), partial molal heat capacity etc. For example structure makers are shown to decrease the fluidity of water (by causing an increase in reorientation time and an increase in viscosity). The reverse is true for structure breakers. It has been shown by these methods that ions of simple electrolytes such as LiF and MgCl₂ having high charge density act as net structure makers and ions with low charge density such as those of CsI and KBr behave as net structure breakers. Frank and Wen²⁵ (Fig. 8) in order to explain these phenomena visualized a picture in which an ion is surrounded by concentric regions of water-molecules. The innermost region 'A' consists of water molecules - polarised, in the usual way by the ionic field which at this range will be relatively weak. The intermediate region 'B' is the region in which water is less ice-like i.e. more

randomly arranged than the normal water. The decreased structure in this region is presumably due to the approximate balance of two competing forces, namely, the normal structure orienting influence of the neighbouring water molecules, and the radially orienting influence of the electric field of the ion. Ions with low charge density have relatively weak electrostatic field, which makes the region 'A' very small thereby causing net decrease in structure. In the case of structure making ions of high charge density the region 'A' of immobilisation exceeds region 'B' which results in a net structural increase around these ions.

Fig. 3. Frank-Wen zone model of water in the neighbourhood of a simple ion. From : Ref. 16.

An entirely different kind of behaviour is shown by non-polar solutes such as hydrocarbons and solutes having non-polar groups with one or two functional groups such as substituted hydrocarbons, quaternary ammonium salts, alcohols, ethers, ketones, etc⁷. The interaction of such solutes with water is known as hydrophobic hydration the origin of which I discussed in the beginning of my lecture while referring to the low solubility of hydrocarbons. Thus, hydrophobic hydration is not simply limited to pure hydrocarbons but is applicable to solutes with functional groups also, provided they have large nonpolar groups attached to them. Such solutes behave like hydrocarbons and the presence of a functional group does not affect their hydrophobicity much. Furthermore high solubility of such compounds in water makes them very convenient to study the phenomenon of hydrophobic hydration and these compounds are therefore preferred over hydrocarbons.

As I pointed out earlier, the dissolution of the hydrophobic compounds in water is governed by entropy factors, and the process is actually accompanied by large entropy decrease and a large increase in partial molal heat capacity of the compound. The large decrease in entropy indicates a small number of configurational states for a given energy which means that the packing of water molecules around dissolved groups is somewhat tighter than in pure water. This situation is treated

as enhancement in the structure of water. However, one must realise that the abnormally low partial molal entropies of solution of non-polar solutes need not originate exclusively from a decrease in the number of configurations available to solvent molecules. Most probably a contribution towards $-\bar{S}_2$ also arises from the changes in the occupancies of the hydrogen bonded vibrational and librational energy levels⁴⁰. Increase in structure by non-polar solutes only means that the number of hydrogen bonds is greater than in water and sometime this has been termed as iceberg formation. According to Frank and Wen²⁵, structure that is formed around the nonpolar solutes may or may not be ice like i.e. similar to the structure existing in pure water at low temperatures. There is no direct evidence for the formation of icebergs or cages around solutes containing nonpolar groups. However, the most impressive evidence for the formation of some kind of definite structure in aqueous solution is probably the existence of solid gas hydrates and clathrates. The view that the hydrophobic hydration consists of fluctuating cage structures also seems to receive some support from the recent ultrasonic absorption studies on aqueous solutions of some organic solutes. The question as to what kind of this enhanced structure is remains thus unanswered though some progress has been made in this direction. There are many physico-chemical methods which can give insight into the structure of aqueous solutions. I will mainly discuss the results of thermodynamic investigations. For understanding hydrophobic hydration it is important that the studies are made on infinitely dilute aqueous solutions as, in such solutions, only the solute-solvent interactions are involved, the solute-solute interactions being negligible.

The heat capacity changes ΔC_p° and the partial molal heat capacities of solutes in water $C_{p,2}^\circ$ reflect structural changes in solutions. For example, the partial molal heat capacity of Bu_4NBr (Table 1) is

TABLE—1. HEAT CAPACITIES OF TETRA-*n*-BUTYLAMMONIUM BROMIDE SALTS IN VARIOUS SOLVENT SYSTEMS

Compound	Solvent	$C_{p,2}^\circ / \text{JK}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$
Bu_4NBr	H_2O	1177 ± 17
Bu_4NBr	D_2O	1249 ± 2
Bu_4NBr	Formamide	578 ± 13
Bu_4NBr	M-Methylformamide	486 ± 17
Bu_4NBr	N, N-Dimethylformamide	553 ± 17
Bu_4NBr	Ethanol	453 ± 22

substantially greater in water relative to nonaqueous solvent⁴¹. A positive value of ΔC_p° would mean the enhancement of hydrogen bonded structure in water since in that case more energy is required to melt the so called structure in solution than in water. A negative value of ΔC_p° on the other hand indicates decrease in the structure of water.

We have in our laboratory set up a calorimeter assembly to determine precise and accurate integral enthalpies of solution of model compounds in water at very low concentrations^{4,2}. The schematic diagram of the set up is given in Fig. 9. Thermistor which forms one arm of the wheatstone bridge is used as a temperature sensing element. The other arms consist of precision decade resistances boxes. With this set up we can detect temperature changes

Fig. 9. Block diagram for calorimetric set up.

of the order of 2×10^{-5} degree. From enthalpies of solution at different temperatures are derived the heat capacity changes

$$\Delta C_p^\circ = \left(\frac{\partial \Delta H}{\partial T} \right)_p = \frac{\Delta H(T_2) - \Delta H_s(T_1)}{(T_2 - T_1)}$$

The values of heat capacity changes ΔC_p° are combined with the heat capacity of pure solutes, \bar{C}_{p2} (available in the literature) to obtain partial molal heat capacities ($\bar{C}_{p2}^\circ = \Delta C_p^\circ + C_{p2}$).

In our initial studies of hydrophobic hydration we used quaternary ammonium halide salts^{4,2-4,6}. These electrolytes behave like hydrocarbons in so far as the hydrophobic effect of these solutes is concerned and have the advantage of being highly soluble in water and thus convenient to study. As a consequence, thermodynamics of the aqueous solutions of R_4N^+ salts is one of the most widely studied aspects of the field of structure of aqueous solutions. Our studies (Table 2) on R_4N^+ salts showed that the dissolution of R_4N^+ salts in water results in positive ΔC_p° values indicating that these solutes cause enhancement in the structure of water. Further the ΔC_p° value is found to increase with the increase in the chain length of the nonpolar groups in these molecules indicating that the structure increasing propensity of the R_4N^+ salts increases with the size of the cation the order being

The increase in ΔC_p° observed is estimated and found to be of the order of $60-90 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ per CH_2 group. A similar situation exists with respect

TABLE—2. VALUES OF HEAT CAPACITY CHANGES ON DISSOLUTION ΔC_p° IN WATER FOR VARIOUS TETRAALKYL AND ARYL SALTS AND INCREMENTS IN \bar{C}_{p2}° PER $-\text{CH}_2-$ GROUP

Compound	ΔC_p° $\text{JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ 30°	\bar{C}_{p2}° (CH_2) $\text{JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ 30°
Me ₄ NI	69±25	57
Et ₄ NI	157±17	76
Pr ₄ NI	499±17	
Me ₄ NBr	-42±17	46
Et ₄ NBr	138±12	84
Pr ₄ NBr	472±9	71
Bu ₄ NBr	750±17	126
Am ₄ NBr	1254±34	
Bu ₄ PBi	779±14	
NaBPh ₄	708±13	
Ph ₄ PBr	611±9	
Ph ₄ ASCl	712±17	

to aromatic hydrophobic salts and the ΔC_p° values obtained for sodium tetraphenylboron and tetraphenyl arsonium and phosphonium chlorides are 714, 798 and 714 $\text{JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively indicating that these solutes are strong structure makers.

It was thought of interest to see how the anionic nonpolar moiety affects the water structure. For this purpose sodium salts of carboxylates were found to form a suitable set of model compounds as they could be easily prepared, are highly soluble in water, and less expensive. The heat capacity results of alkyl sodium carboxylates⁴⁷ indicate that sodium formate is a structure breaker, sodium acetate, a slightly structure maker and higher homologous salts could be labelled as structure makers. The ΔC_p° values as a function of number of carbon atoms are given in Fig. 10. The linear slope gives a uniform increment of $60 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ in ΔC_p° value per CH_2 group which is consistent with other classes of compounds.

However, the results on aryl sodium carboxylates indicate a much smaller increment (about 6 cal $\text{deg}^{-1} \text{ mole}^{-1}$) per CH_2 group. This reduced effect has been attributed to the presence of π electrons in the phenyl ring. The methyl and phenyl groups have opposite inductive effects on the charge of the

functional group $\left(\begin{array}{c} \text{O} \\ \parallel \\ -\text{C} \\ | \\ \text{O}^- \end{array} \right)$. The inductive effect of

the phenyl ring acts so as to increase the polarity of

the CH_2 group (located between $\begin{array}{c} \text{O} \\ \parallel \\ -\text{C} \\ | \\ \text{O}^- \end{array}$ and phenyl

groups), thus reducing its positive contribution to ΔC_p° .

Fig. 10. Heat capacity change on dissolution, ΔC_p° at infinite dilution in water for some sodium carboxylates versus total number of carbon atoms in alkyl and aryl groups at 30° .

As mentioned by me in the beginning of the discussion, hydrophobic hydration is of crucial importance in understanding the conformations of proteins. Since amino acids are the main constituents of protein and polypeptides, it was therefore felt that the systematic study of their hydrophobic hydration effect would hopefully be of great significance in understanding the conformation of protein structures. Heat capacity studies of aqueous solutions of amino acids⁴⁶ could also throw light on the effect of the presence of two functional groups on the hydrophobicity of nonpolar groups attached to them. In addition, since these amino acids are zwitterions, by considering various amino acids in which the functional groups NH_3^+ and COO^- are attached at both ends of the nonpolar hydrocarbon chain, the effect of charge separation on the hydrophobicity of the molecule can also be studied. Thus these acids form a good model system not only for studying quantitatively the effect of two charged groups on hydrophobic hydration but also the effect of changing their relative positions.

Values of $\Delta \bar{C}_{p2}^\circ$ and \bar{C}_{p2}° at 30° for amino acids⁴⁸ are illustrated in Fig. 11 as a function of the number of carbon atoms in the alkyl chain. For these acids, one observes a uniform increment of $67 \text{ JK}^{-1}\text{mol}^{-1}$ and $88 \text{ JK}^{-1}\text{mol}^{-1}$ per CH_2 group in $\Delta \bar{C}_{p2}^\circ$ and \bar{C}_{p2}° respectively at 30° . It is interesting to note that the increment in $\Delta \bar{C}_{p2}^\circ$ and

\bar{C}_{p2}° per CH_2 group observed here is the same as has been found earlier in various homologous series of monofunctional compounds such as aliphatic carboxylic acids, and their sodium salts, ethers, amines and alcohols etc.⁴⁹⁻⁵³ (Fig. 12) Since an increase in the value of $\Delta \bar{C}_{p2}^\circ$ and \bar{C}_{p2}° is associated with an increase in the hydrophobic hydration effect, the uniform increase in $\Delta \bar{C}_{p2}^\circ$ and \bar{C}_{p2}° for the CH_2 group increment indicates that the

Fig. 11. Heat capacity change on dissolution and partial molal heat capacity of α -amino acids and ω -amino acids at 30° as a function of number of carbon atoms in the alkyl chain.

hydrophobic hydration or structure enhancing propensity of α -amino acids increases with alkyl chain length and that the electrostriction effect (structure breaking effect) due to dipolar character remains constant and independent of the alkyl chain length.

However, for homologous series of amino acids where the NH_3^+ group is at the terminal position (ω -amino acids), the situation is different. The results on heat capacities of these ω -amino acids⁴⁸ as shown in Fig. 11 indicate that unlike in the case of α -amino acids the increase in $\Delta \bar{C}_{p2}^\circ$ and \bar{C}_{p2}° per CH_2 group is not uniform but rather decreases systematically in the following order :

From the data in Table 3 it has been observed⁴⁸ (Fig. 13) that the shift of an NH_3^+ group from α to β position reduces the value of $\Delta \bar{C}_{p2}^\circ$ and \bar{C}_{p2}° by about $54 \pm 5 \text{ JK}^{-1}\text{mol}^{-1}$. However, the shift of an NH_3^+ group from β to γ position results in a lower reduction (about $28 \text{ JK}^{-1}\text{mol}^{-1}$) but none the less still significant. The effect continues till

TABLE—3. VALUES OF ΔC_p° AND C_p° OF ISOMERS OF SOME AMINO ACIDS IN WATER.

Amino Acids	ΔC_p° JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹ 30°C	C_p° JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹ 25°C	$\overline{C_p^\circ}$ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹ 30°C
α -Aminobutyric acid	86±17	146	232±17
α -Isoaminobutyric acid	90±12	146	236±12
β -Aminobutyric acid	36±8	146	182±8
β -Isoaminobutyric acid	28±5	146	174±5
DL-Norvaline	166±17	168	334±17
L-Valine	143±19	168	311±19
DL-Norleucine	199±2	201	400±2
L-Leucine	201±17	201	402±17

ϵ -position where the over all decrease in ΔC° or $\overline{C_p^\circ}$ turns out to be about 100 JK⁻¹mol⁻¹. These results indicate that when the charged groups are separated by varying distances in these ω -amino acids, their mutual interactions interfere with hydrophobic hydration of the nonpolar groups located in between them and the linearity of the hydrophobic character with respect to chain length to be exhibited by these groups is destroyed as indicated by nonlinearity relationship between the heat capacity and the number of carbon atoms in the chain length (Fig. 11). At the same time, the heat capacity data on ξ -aminoheptanoic acid and η -aminooctanoic acid suggest that when the separation of the charged groups NH₃⁺ and COO⁻ exceeds about five bond lengths, then the interactions of the charged groups with the solvent are no longer modified by their mutual interactions, as evidenced by the normal contribution of a CH₂ group ($\Delta C_p = 70$ JK⁻¹mol⁻¹) beyond ϵ -aminohexanoic acid.

Fig. 12. Partial molal heat capacity of various homologous series of compounds as a function of number of carbon atoms in the alkyl chain.

There is a controversy about the effect of branching of the alkyl chain on the heat capacity of the nonpolar molecules⁵⁴⁻⁵⁶. It was opined by some people that nonpolar molecules containing straight chain groups have higher heat capacities than branched chain organic compounds. To solve this controversy a few isomers of aminoacids namely α -aminobutyric acid and α -aminoisobutyric acid, β -aminobutyric acid and β -isoaminobutyric acid, L-valine and DL-norvaline and L-leucine and DL-norleucine are studied by us. The heat capacity results of these compounds are given in Table 3. The constancy in heat capacity values of these pairs clearly shows that branching of alkyl groups does not affect the partial molal heat capacities and hence the hydrophobic hydration propensity of aminoacids. It is here that heat capacity measurements score over free energy measurements in elucidating structural contributions. Free energy measurements do not conform to the additivity relationship of the independent groups when branched and normal chain isomers are compared. As a general rule ΔG_s° (free energy change for the dissolution process) increases with the number of internal degrees of freedom due to entropic factors⁷.

Fig. 13. Change in partial molal heat capacity as a function of shift of the NH₃⁺ group with respect to the COO⁻ group from α to β , γ , δ , ϵ , ξ , and η positions in some amino acids.

The hydrophilic groups like hydroxyl groups are believed to reduce the hydrophobic propensity of the neighbouring alkyl group^{3,4,1,57}. In order to see quantitatively and qualitatively such an effect, when two functional groups are involved in a molecule, studies are undertaken on some hydroxy amino acids and the results are shown in Table 4. The results point out that on an average for all the compounds studied, the substitution of H by OH

group results in a decrease of about $26 \pm 8 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ in \bar{C}_{p2} in the neighbouring CH_2 group. A similar decrease in \bar{C}_{p2} and hence a reduction in the hydrophobic character of the neighbouring nonpolar moiety of many compounds was observed by others when hydrophobic groups are introduced into the alkyl chain attached to a single functional group⁴¹.

Ternary Systems :

In recent years studies on ternary systems of aqueous solutions are gaining popularity because it is sometimes difficult to arrive at any definite conclusion from studies on the binary systems alone. The ternary system should act as a better example than the binary system for the interesting studies on the reaction mechanisms and rates solvolysis of certain organic compounds in mixed aqueous solvents and on the denaturation of proteins by certain reagents, since both these studies are carried out as ternary systems. In a ternary system the properties of a model compound are studied in an aqueous binary solvent system, in order to determine the response of the modified water structure caused by the cosolvent to the presence of the model compound.

Results based on the studies of ternary systems⁵⁸⁻⁶² have in some instances supported and in others contradicted the conclusions arrived at from the properties of binary systems.

Fig. 14. Enthalpy of solution of Am_4NBr (ref. 55) NaBPh_4 (ref. 52) and Bu_4NBr (ref. 54) in t-butyl alcohol-water mixtures.

TABLE-4. HYDROXYL GROUP SUBSTITUTION EFFECT ON ΔC_p° AND \bar{C}_{p2}° OF SOME AMINO ACIDS.

Group Substitution in Amino Acid.	Amino Acids involved	$\Delta C_p^\circ, \text{JK}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$ 30°	$\bar{C}_{p2}^\circ, \text{JK}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$ 30°
$\text{CH}_3 \longrightarrow \text{CH}_2\text{OH}$	DL-Serine- DL-Alanine	-24	-13
$\text{CH}_3 \longrightarrow \text{CH}_2\text{OH}$	L-Threonine- DL-Amino- butyric Acid	-22	-21
$\text{CH}_3 \longrightarrow \text{CHOH}$	L-Hydroxyl- proline- DL-Proline.	-32	-28

Arnett et. al.⁵⁸ have made detailed thermodynamic studies on a series of normal and amphiphilic electrolytes. Endothermic maxima for enthalpies of solution have been observed for all solutes regardless of their size, charge or substituent groups and the position of the maxima is dependent only on the cosolvent being nearly independent of the solute. However, our recent studies⁶⁰⁻⁶¹ on the transfer of Bu_4NBr and Am_4NBr from water to aqueous solvent mixtures indicate that the solute also plays an important role in determining the trend of enthalpies (Fig. 14) and heat capacities (Fig. 15) of the solutes as a function of the cosolvent composition. The enthalpy and heat capacity maxima are explained in terms of model adopted

for interpreting the similar extrema in properties such as partial molal volume and sound absorption of the aqueous solutions of the cosolvent in binary system^{61,63}. For example the maxima in heat capacity of hydrophobic solutes Am_4NBr , Bu_4NBr and NaBPh_4 around 0.04 mole fraction of t-BuOH... is attributed to the stabilization of water structure due to filling up of cavities in water by t-BuOH till 0.04 mole fraction. The sharp decrease in ΔC_p° (more than $600 \text{ cal mole}^{-1}$ in case of NaBPh_4) on further addition of t-BuOH has been explained to be due to collapse of the structure arising from t-BuOH being no longer able to be accommodated in the cavities of solvent water, though no concrete proof is available for speculation to the theory of formation of clathrates corresponding to this composition.

One of the most useful applications of the study of ternary systems is in the role of water in denaturation of proteins in aqueous solutions of

Fig. 15. Heat capacity of dissolution of Am_4NBr (ref. 55), NaBPh_4 (ref. 52) and Bu_4NBr (ref. 54) in t-butyl alcohol-water mixtures.

protein denaturants such as urea. Protein denaturation is one of the most interesting and complex biological processes that is not yet completely understood. The present day knowledge of the mechanism of the protein denaturation is essentially an extrapolation of model compound data. In spite of numerous studies on various protein denaturants solutions the exact mechanism is not yet understood. In fact whether there is any single mechanism for denaturation caused by urea class of denaturants is an open question. On one hand there is evidence that urea binds to the proteins directly^{64,65}. Alternatively, the role played by the change in the structure of water by the denaturant in the denaturation process has also been proposed. Even here, unfortunately in spite of many a data, there is no unanimity of opinion as to the exact nature of effect of urea on the structure of water⁶³⁻⁶⁶. The views of biochemists tend towards water structure breaking,^{7,67} while dielectric constant studies have been interpreted in terms of structure promotion by urea⁶⁸, heat capacity and ultrasonic absorption measurements indicate a small decrease in the structure of water in the presence of urea⁶⁹⁻⁷¹ at low temperatures. Results based on the properties of ternary systems such as the effect of urea on the solubilities of hydrocarbons⁷² and R_4N^+ salts in water⁷³ and on critical concentration of certain surfactants⁷⁴, support the view that urea breaks water structure and this tendency increases with increase in urea concentration. The heat capacity of transfer $\Delta C_{p_{tr}}$ for Bu_4NBr and Am_4NBr from water to urea is found to be negative becoming

more negative with increase in urea concentration (Fig. 16) classifying urea as a structure breaker at

Fig. 16. Heat capacity of transfer for Am_4NBr , Bu_4NBr and NaBPh_4 from water to concentrated aqueous urea solutions at 30° .

all concentrations^{62,75,76}. These results support the model proposed by Frank and Franks⁷⁷ in which urea is termed as statistical structure breaker and the structure breaking action of urea is due to the dissolution of urea in the dense monomer species of water, causing a shift of some water clusters into non-bonded molecules.

The structure breaking action of urea in water is also supported by the study of ternary systems containing electrolytes. For example, if a concentrated aqueous urea solution is less structured than pure water, then the addition of structure breaking solutes such as common electrolytes (hydrophilic salts) should be accompanied by a decrease in their structure breaking capacity. In other words, the transfer of structure breaking solutes from water to aqueous urea solutions should be accompanied by an increase in heat capacity and endothermic heat changes. In fact, there is evidence though fragmentary in support of this in the literature⁷⁸⁻⁸⁰.

The preliminary results of our work on the transfer properties of amino acids from water to aqueous urea solutions also indicate that the interaction of urea with the region showing hydrophobic interactions can be distinguished clearly from other interactions in these amino acids.

Using the studies on similar ternary systems, we have also made some attempts to look into the

possibilities of a correlation existing between the effectiveness of solutes in reducing hydrophobic hydration and their effectiveness in protein denaturation. The results (Fig. 17) on the heat capacities of

Fig. 17. Heat capacity of transfer of Bu₄NBr from water to aqueous sodium chloride, potassium chloride, urea and guanidine hydrochloride solutions at 30°.

transfer of Bu₄NBr and Am₄NBr from water to aqueous solutions of NaCl, KCl, urea and GuHCl indicate that the increasing order of

in effectiveness of reducing hydrophobic hydration (as indicated by the negative ΔC_{ptr} values) or structure promoting ability of Bu₄NBr and Am₄NBr correlates well with the increasing effectiveness of these solutes in protein denaturation⁶².

References

1. W. KAUZMANN, *Advan. Protein Chem.*, 1959, 14, 1.
2. C. TANFORD, *Advan. Protein Chem.*, 1968, 23, 121.
3. C. TANFORD, *Advan. Protein Chem.* 1970, 24, 1.
4. C. TANFORD, "The Hydrophobic Effect", New York, Wiley, 1973.
5. H. S. FRANK and M. W. EVANS, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1945, 13, 507.
6. F. FRANKS and D. J. G. IVES. *Quart. Rev.*, (London), 1966, 20, 1.
7. "Water-Comprehensive Treatise", Vol. 4. (F. Franks, ed), Plenum Press, New York, London, 1975.
8. "Water-Comprehensive Treatise" (F. Franks, Ed.) ; Vol. 1, Plenum Press, New York, London, 1972.
9. D. EISENBERG and W. KAUZMANN, "The Structure and Properties of Water", Oxford University Press, Oxford and New York, 1969.
10. J.L. KAVANAU, "Water and Solute-Water Interactions", San Francisco, 1964.
11. R. A. HORNE, "Marine Chemistry", Wiley Interscience, 1969.

12. H. S. FRANK, *Science*, 1970, 169, 635.
13. H.S. FRANK, *Proc. Roy. Soc. (London)*, 1958, A247, 481.
14. H. S. FRANK, *Feb. Proc.* 24, No. 2, Part III, P. S-1, 1965.
15. O. T. SAMOILOV, "Structure of Aqueous Electrolyte Solutions and the Hydration of Ions" (translated by D. J. G. Ives). Consultants Bureau, New York, 1965.
16. I. M. KLOTZ, "Water. Its fitness as a Molecular Environment", in "Membranes and Ion transport" Vol. 1, Chapter 4, Ed, Edward Bittar, Wiley Interscience, London, 1970.
17. T. S. SARMA and J. C. AHLUWALIA, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 1973, 2, 203.
18. J. C. AHLUWALIA and C. N. R. RAO, *J. Sci. Ind. Res. (India)*, 1971, 30, 453.
19. A. BEN-NAIM, *Water and Aqueous Solutions-Introduction to a Molecular Theory*, Plenum, New York, 1974.
20. MU SHIK, JOHN and HENRY EYRING, *Ann. Rev. Phys. Chem.*; 1976, 27, 45.
21. J. D. BERNAL and R. H. FOWLER, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1935, 1, 515.
22. J. MORGAN and B. E. WARREN, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1938, 6, 666.
23. J. LENNARD JONES and J. A. POPLE, *Proc. Roy. Soc. (London)*, 1951, A202, 155.
24. J. A. POPLE, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, (London), 1951, A205, 163.
25. H. S. FRANK and W. Y. WEN, *Disc. Faraday Soc.*, 1957, 24, 133.
26. H. S. FRANK and A. S. QUIST, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1961, 34, 604.
27. G. NEMETHY and H. A. SCHERAGA. *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1962, 36, 3382, 3401.
28. R. P. MARCHI and H. EYRING, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1964, 68, 221.
29. G. E. WALRAFEN, in "Hydrogen-Bonded Solvent System" (Eds.) A. K. COVINGTON and P. JONES, Taylor and Francis, London 1968, Page. 9.
30. M. D. DANFORD and H. A. LEVY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 84, 3965.
31. A. H. NARTEN, M. D. DANFORD and H. A. LEVY, *Disc. Faraday Soc.*, 1967, 43, 97.
32. L. PAULING. "The Nature of the Chemical Bond, "3rd Ed., Cornell University Press, Ithaca, New York, 1960.
33. C. M. DAVIS and T. A. LITOVITZ., *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1965, 42, 2563.
34. V. VAND and W. A. SENIOR, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1965, 43, 1878.
35. A. RAHMAN and F.H. STILLINGER, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1971, 55, 3336.
36. F. H. STILLINGER and A. RAHMAN, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1972, 57, 1281.
37. A. RAHMAN and F. H. STILLINGER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 95, 7943.
38. F. H. STILLINGER and A. RAHMAN, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1974, 60, 1554.
39. A. RAHMAN, F. H. STILLINGER and H. L. LEMBERG, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1975, 63, 5223.
40. F. FRANKS, in "Hydrogen Bonded Solvent Systems" ed. A. K. COVINGTON and P. JONES, Taylor Francis, London, 1968, p. 224.
41. G. RIALDI and R. L. BILTONEN in "International Review of Science, Physical Chemistry, "Series 2, Vol. 10, (Ed.) H. A. SKINNER, Butterworths, London, 1975.
42. S. SUBRAMANIAN and J. C. AHLUWALIA, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1968, 72, 2525.
43. T. S. SARMA and J. C. AHLUWALIA, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1971, 67, 2528.
44. T. S. SARMA, R. K. MOHANTY and J. C. AHLUWALIA, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1969, 65, 2533.
45. T. S. SARMA and J. C. AHLUWALIA. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1970, 74, 1547.
46. R. K. MOHANTY and J. C. AHLUWALIA, *J. Chem. Thermodyn.*, 1972, 4, 532.
47. B. CHAWLA and J. C. AHLUWALIA, *J. Solution Chem.*, 1975, 4, 383.
48. K. P. PRASAD and J. C. AHLUWALIA, *J. Solution Chem.*, 1976, 5, 491.

J. C. AHLUWALIA : THERMODYNAMICS OF HYDROPHOBIC HYDRATION

49. KONICEK and I. WADSO., *Acta. Chem. Scand.*, 1971, **25**, 1541.
50. K. KUSANO, J. SUURKUUSK and I. WADSO, *J. Chem. Thermodyn.*, 1973, **7**, 757.
51. E. M. ARNETT, B. KOVER and J. V. CARTER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **91**, 4028.
52. D. M. ALEXANDER and D. J. T. HILL, *Austral J. Chem.* 1969, **22**, 347.
53. S. CABANI, G. CONTI, E. MATTEOLI and A. TONI, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans I*, 1977, **73**, 476.
54. N. NICHOLS, R. SKOLD, C. SPINK, J. SUURKUUSK and I. WADSO, *J. Chem. Thermodyn.*, 1976, **8**, 1081.
55. G. C. KRESHECK and L. BENJAMIN, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1964, **68**, 2476.
56. C. H. SPINK and I. WADSO, *J. Chem. Thermodyn.*, 1975, **7**, 561.
57. E. J. COHN and J. T. EDSALL, "Proteins, Amino Acids and Peptides", Reinhold, New York, 1943.
58. E. M. ARNETT, in "Physico-Chemical Processes in Mixed Aqueous Solvents", (Ed.) F. FRANKS, Heinemann, London, 1967, p. 105.
59. J. F. BRANDTS in "Structure and Stability of Biological Macromolecules", Eds., S. M. TIMASHEFF and G. D. FASMAN, Marcell Dekker, Inc., New York, 1969, p. 213.
60. R. K. MOHANTY, T. S. SARMA, S. SUBRAMANIAN and J. C. AHLUWALIA, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1971, **67**, 305.
61. R. K. MOHANTY, S. SUNDER and J. C. AHLUWALIA, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1972, **76**, 2577.
62. B. CHAWLA, S. SUNDER and J. C. AHLUWALIA, *J. Phys. Chem.* 1973, **77**, 2335.
63. F. FRANKS in "Hydrogen Bonded Solvent System", Eds. A. K. COVINGTON and P. JONES, Taylor and Francis, London, 1968, p. 42.
64. H. B. BULL and K. BREESE, *Arch. Biophys.*, 1970, **139**, 93.
65. E. P. K. HADE and C. TANFORD, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 5034.
66. A. HOLTZER and M. F. EMERSON, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1969, **73**, 26.
67. J. F. BRANDTS, *J. Chem. Soc.* 1964, **86**, 4302.
68. M. ABU-HAMDIYYAH, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1965, **69**, 2720.
69. S. SUBRAMANIAN, D. BALASUBRAMANIAN and J. C. AHLUWALIA, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1969, **73**, 266.
70. S. SUBRAMANIAN, T. S. SARMA, D. BALASUBRAMANIAN and J. C. AHLUWALIA, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1971, **75**, 815.
71. K. ARAKAWA and N. TAKENAKA, *Bull. Chem. Soc.*, Japan, 1967, **40**, 2739.
72. D. B. WETLAUFER S. K. MALIK, L. STOLLER and R. L. COFFIN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **86**, 508.
73. F. FRANKS and D. L. CLARKE, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1967, **71**, 1155.
74. M. J. SCHICK, *J. Phys. Chem.* 1964, **68**, 3585.
75. T. S. SARMA and J. C. AHLUWALIA, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1972, **76**, 1366.
76. B. CHAWLA and J. C. AHLUWALIA, *J. C. S. Faraday I*, 1973, **69**, 434.
77. H. S. FRANK and F. FRANKS, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1968, **48**, 4746.
78. N. DESROSIERS, G. PERRON, J. G. MATHIESON, B. E. CONWAY, and J. E. DESNOYERS, *J. Solution. Chem.*, 1974, **3**, 789.
79. J. H. STERN and J. D. KULLUK, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1969, **73**, 2795.
80. Y. YON POINTUD and J. JUILLARD, *J. C. S. Faraday I*, 1977, **73**, 1.